

A COMPARISON OF DEEP LEARNING MODELS FOR EELGRASS MEADOWS MONITORING.

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Abstract

The development of imaging technology provides novel opportunities for monitoring and management of marine ecosystems. Biological management programs need improvement due to the fast-changing conditions of the environments they monitor. Current climate change and other anthropogenic pressures are causing impacts in many key marine habitats and species. Eelgrass meadows are one of the communities that acts as main carbon sinks, therefore, their protection and monitoring is of great importance.

In this study the combination of Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV's) with the deep learning algorithms was explored to test if it could support benthic vegetation monitoring. Several computer vision models were developed, training them to be capable of analysing information from different sites with similar habitats and retrieving accurate maps of benthic vegetation.

Results showed that computer vision models can reliably represent the presence-absence of seagrass meadows. For abundance estimations, more research or different concepts are needed. Regarding time optimization, when aimed at monitoring one species, the usage of computer vision models was deemed as equally optimal. However, when used for several species, this methodology would be a substantial step forward in ecosystem monitoring. The overall conclusion of this study is that deep learning machines can aid in the monitoring of sites, providing information regarding species presence, extent, maximum depth, and perhaps density. This opens new perspectives for studying marine ecosystems dynamics and restoration.

Introduction

Oceans and seas are currently undergoing important and constant changes that are decreasing their overall health. These variations are caused by climate change through the increase in global temperature, the acidification of the ocean, the loss of biodiversity and more. As humans are the main cause of these impacts, there is a constant need to develop science and technology (Arias et al. 2021). With them society can assess which environments are more vulnerable and which hold the most importance when it comes to opposing climate change. Oceans are known as a “carbon pump”, as they sink around 25% of the carbon produced by humans (Gruber et al., 2023; Ocean & Climate Platform, 2020; United Nations, s. f.). Therefore, the biological, physical and chemical components of marine environments are highly important and must be preserved for a proper ecological function. This has been recognized by many governments and studied by academia and institutions, which has derived in directives, laws and projects. The focus of these actions is the preservation and protection of marine habitats, mainly through long-term standardized records, and constant management and monitoring of the environment (Airoidi and Beck, 2007; IPCC, 2023; OSPAR, 2021).

To oversee constantly changing habitats there must be reliable records, which may include biodiversity inventories, species richness, genetic richness, alien species, etc. Having a well-established monitoring system that tracks long periods of time will allow to easily detect changes in the environment, such as population decreases, appearance of pressures or known drivers of change. Despite the amount of apparatus and methodology available, some of the main restraints are resources like time and funding. And since oceans are vast and deep, some of the previously mentioned methods can take years to gather information. In the case of eelgrass meadows, monitoring efforts can take several weeks, and restoration projects can take up to 10 years (Moksnes et al., 2021). A derived obstacle is the amount of data obtained through surveys or sampling campaigns. Where even after filtering and cleaning the information, thousands of gigabytes of material remain, becoming an issue of high importance.

As mentioned previously, oceans hold high value due to their influence on the carbon cycle and climate change, but there is more to it. The focus of this study, eelgrass meadows, are habitat engineers, highly relevant for carbon sink, development of sediments, supply of shelter, and much more (Dahl et al., 2023). Nevertheless, this habitat has suffered big losses throughout the decades as proven by several studies; and in some cases, it continues to do (Airoidi and Beck, 2007; de los Santos, 2019; Moksnes and Bergström, 2025; Waycott et al., 2009). Despite the importance of this habitat and its registered decline, it is labelled as “least concern” (IUCN red list, 2024). This can be problematic, as eelgrass meadows are conformed by one main species – *Zostera marina*, *Zostera japonica*, *Zostera noltei*, etc -, making them highly susceptible to pandemics, for example the “wasting disease”. This disease killed 90% of eelgrass meadows in the North Atlantic Ocean in the 30s (Waycott et al., 2009; Moore and Short, 2006). Since then, some European areas continued to lose 40 to 60% of the total coverage and showed a constant decrease up until recent years. This also applies to the Swedish Skagerrak coast (de los Santos, 2019; Nyqvist et al, 2009), where this study was performed. Due to this continuous loss and the importance of seagrass, there are active efforts to restore and monitor the remaining meadows. The current methodology for monitoring consists on using aerial images - obtained with a drone or satellites - to delimit the main area and then examine the marine vegetation through snorkelling, drop cams or using aquascopes. This is susceptible to weather, technical and biological conditions. For example, if aerial

imagery is not available all the work will have to be done “manually”, causing it to be less efficient and more expensive (Berglund et al., 2023, Moksnes et al., 2021).

To overcome the issues mentioned in the previous paragraphs, recent studies are developing new monitoring methods aimed not only at being more cost-efficient and safer, but also at identifying ecosystem components, warranting more profound inspections of the oceans (Loureiro et al., 2024). One of these new methodologies involves the use of ROV (Jessop et al., 2024) and image analysis (Bean et al., 2017; Danovaro et al., 2016). It has been highly tested and used to identify fish and topics related to them (Hamzaoui et al., 2023; Saleh et al., 2023; Salman et al., 2019; Sokolova et al., 2023) setting a precedent for other areas. Nowadays, some of the focus is shifting from fish to eelgrass meadows (Nielsen et al., 2023; Noman et al., 2024; Tahara et al., 2022) but it is a slow change. Nevertheless, the aim of these studies is to combine several new methods to decrease the need for resources for monitoring programs. One of the possible outcomes is that these huge amounts of data, that currently take months to analyse, could be evaluated in a matter of minutes, all thanks to powerful models based on deep learning machines. If consistently proven effective, it could support long-term studies, as having a standardized methodology will grant stronger evidence of change, be it of loss, recovery or stabilization.

Therefore, the challenges not only reside in how nature is observed, but also in how it is processed and the components considered. As digital technology develops, new algorithms are created, reaching higher processing capabilities that allow scientists to work with huge amounts of data. However, like every developing area and as Loureiro et al. (2024) discussed, there is still a long process to fulfill, from diversifying resources to optimizing the equipment at hand. Based on the current instruments and knowledge available, the aim of this report is to showcase the development and training of machine learning (ML) models based on imagery recorded with a ROV. Comparing its capability to classify different species present in the environment and representing the extent and density of the meadows. With the final objective of selecting the one or ones that allow for more cost-effective monitoring and management of *Zostera marina*.

Methodology

Dataset

Figure 1. Schematic of the ROV survey setup (Chasing Gladius Mini S with quadrat over an eelgrass meadow). Illustrative diagram, used during Autumn fieldwork. Saga Alsterlind, 2024.

The data used to train all the models was acquired using a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) Chasing Gladius Mini S (Figure 1). The sites visited were Kristineberg Marine Laboratory and Borno's Oceanographic Station; where the maximum depth reached during the recordings was 6 meters. Kristineberg dataset was acquired during October 2024, while Borno dataset during April 2025. Datasets (Table 1) are divided based on the frame quality, Kristineberg 720p, Kristineberg 4K and Borno 720p. All the annotations were done using BIIGLE (Zurowietz & Nattkemper, 2021).

The datasets are split based on a 70/20/10 proportion, where 70% is the training set, 20% is the validation set and 10% is the test set. The code used to make this division was instructed to put at least one annotation of each class into each split. If not possible, the train and test set were priorities, being train the highest one.

Dataset	Size	Annotations
Kristineberg 720p (K)	128 frames	536
Kristineberg 4K (K)	57 frames	278
Borno 720p (B)	61+19 frames*	148+52*

Table 1. Resume of the dataset used for training the different models. The models' names are based on the origin of the data, being Kristineberg shortened to K and Borno to B. * Although the same compilation of random frames was used when annotating, the first set was annotated using list 1, and the second set using list 2 – Table 2

Classes

With the objective of improving future adaptation to unseen environments, each classification catalogue, generic and reduced (R), was used in two different datasets, Kristineberg (K) and Kristineberg combined with Bornö (KB). This led to the training of four instance segmentation (IS) models (Table 2).

List 1	List 2 (Reduced – R)
It contains a wide variety of categories, making them generic models	A more focused list, oriented to ecosystem species or specifics that signal healthy environments
K-IS; KB-IS	K-IS-R; KB-IS-R
Abiotic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fine grained sand • Gravel • Rocks Biotic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epiphyte • Filamentous green algae • <i>Fucus serratus</i> * • <i>Halidrys siliquosa</i> ** • <i>Laminaria spp</i> ** • Phaeophyceae * • Rhodophyta * • <i>Ruppia maritima</i> • <i>Ulva spp</i> ** • <i>Zostera marina</i> ! 	Abiotic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard bottom * • Soft bottom Biotic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Arenicola marina</i> • <i>Ceramium spp</i> • Crab ** • Filamentous algae • <i>Fucus serratus</i> • <i>Zostera marina</i> !

Table 2. Classes used in training are based on the purpose they serve. To identify possible bias, the classes were identified in relation to the number of annotations. ! Class with the most annotations. * Classes with few annotations. ** Classes with none or the least number of annotations.

Deep Learning Model

Deep learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), learn visual patterns from annotated image data by adjusting internal parameters during training (Warfield, 2023). These systems can specialize in one subject of your choosing by feeding the correct data in the correct format. learn visual patterns from annotated image data by adjusting internal parameters during training. We chose You Only Look Once (YOLO), using the Ultralytics packages in Python 3.12 (Van Rossum & Python Software Foundation, 2023), for its optimization and user friendliness. Additionally, YOLO builds upon previous versions, addressing the limitations found in old versions (Terven et al., 2023).

Within this architectural family, the version 11 incorporates an optimized version of CSP (Cross Stage Partial) bottleneck and the C2PSA (Cross Stage Partial with Spatial Attention) module – named C3k2 (Ultralytics, 2024).

Regarding the annotation systems for image analysis, instance segmentation was selected due to its high capability to outline shapes. A high proportion of marine vegetation species do not exhibit a clear growth pattern, for example filamentous algae. Nevertheless, there are species or groups with specific features that make them easily identifiable, but when a “bush” appears, the overall image diffuses. The main species of this project, *Zostera marina*, is easily identified due to its long and thin green leaves. Another example would be the *Fucus* genus, which also showed high identification rates.

Training Procedure

The training was done using the platforms provided by EuroHPC Joint Undertaking, which awarded this project access to the EuroHPC supercomputer LUMI, hosted by CSC (Finland) and the LUMI consortium through a EuroHPC Regular Access call.

Instance segmentation

As stated in paragraph 4.1, the images used for the training of these models (Figure 2) were obtained from videos of natural spaces, extracted to be manually analyzed. Since this is a species focused work, most of the footage belongs to eelgrass meadows. However, within possibilities, the annotation process maintained a balance between classes, avoiding an excessive input of one class over the others. Nonetheless, some classes had very few annotations due to the nature of the division and the areas recorded (crabs, *ulva sp*, etc).

The images selected range from high to low definition, and from clear to cloudy days, with the intention of avoiding weather related setbacks. Aiming to make the model usable when used in unfavourable conditions.

Figure 2. Visualization of the manual image analysis executed during data processing for training process (Biigle).

Models

The resulting product was several YOLOv11 models. They were trained using the LUMI platform and the script provided by KSO project¹. Similarly, all models were trained using the medium size base model, provided by Ultralytics, and with a learning rate of 0.1, 1 batch and 100 epochs. The models are divided into “general” (K-IS and KB-IS) and “focused” models (K-IS-R and KB-IS-R). Smaller YOLOv11 variants were not included in the final comparison, but may be relevant in future work given the relatively small annotation set.

Model analysis

This project main objective is to find which model or models can be selected to create monitoring maps used for future management of eelgrass meadows. Therefore, we are interested in high precision and high recall for the *Zostera marina* class, the technical information was obtained from the training script and Weights and Biases, where the run report and artifacts are contained.

Since these models have a biological purpose, there is a high interest in proving their capacity to identify not only eelgrass, but its density. For that reason, a ground truth test was done, where 200 random frames were selected (100 from Kristineberg and 100 from Borno) and manually classified, here the density levels were set in multiples of 5. These same frames were then run through the models and the predictions obtained were compared to the human assessment. Using these results, the values obtained are true positives (TP), true negatives (TN) (human and model results coincide), and false negatives (FN) and false positives (FP) (model under- or overestimates presence or densities). With these scores, precision, accuracy, sensitivity and the F1 score can be calculated (Table 3). From these four, the most important value is the F1 score as it is a combination of precision and sensitivity (Fawcett, 2005; Powers, 2008).

Precision	Accuracy	Sensitivity	F1 score
$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	$\frac{TP + TN}{P + N}$	$\frac{TP}{P}$	$\frac{2 TP}{2 TP + FP + FN}$

Table 3. Formulas used to calculate the values of precision, accuracy, sensitivity and F1 score in the ground truth tests.

Maps

The maps obtained were created using a model implementation script², rasterization script² and QGIS. The first script, written with Python 3.12, implemented the model as a predictive tool. The outcome was then run through the second script, written with R (R version 4.3.1) which created rasters that were visualized with QGIS. Additional maps were Sweden’s map (Lantmateriet, 2024) and eelgrass meadows records (LstO Ålgräs- och natingångar 2019-2024). Bathymetry lines were added using the maps found in Skippo and the vectorial tool in QGIS.

Results

For the technical analysis the model output metrics, obtained during training, were used (Table 4). It is observed that the generalist models (K-IS and KB-IS) display weaker mAP, precision and recall rates due to having more classes which were also more diverse. The

¹ KSO scripts: <https://github.com/ocean-data-factory-sweden/kso.git>

² Report scripts: <https://github.com/PauSowa/Model-Implementation-for-Eelgrass-Meadows-Mapping>

Reduced models (K-IS-R and KB-IS-R) used 9 classes instead of 12, influencing the performance metrics, especially the best performing model, the K-IS-R.

Comparison based on the Metrics for the Model Performance

Model	mAP	Precision	Recall
List 1			
K-IS	43.2	33.3	11.8
KB-IS	44.0*	33.3	22.2
List 2			
K-IS-R	52.0	68.2*	68.2
KB-IS-R	36.0	71.4	45.5*

Table 4. mAP, precision and recall values obtained for the models when training them. Highlighted in bold are the highest values for each section. * Second highest values.

Studying binary ground truth tests (Table 5) - capability of the models to correctly predict presence and absence of *Zostera marina* – the models showed promising performances, with the lowest values being near 50% and reaching a 100%. The highest F1 score was obtained by KB-IS-R, with 91.5%, closely followed by KB-IS, 84.8%.

Ground truth for *Zostera marina* – Binary (presence- absence)

Model	Precision	Accuracy	Sensitivity	F1 score
List 1				
K-IS	93.8	68	50.4	65.6
KB-IS	100	84*	73.6*	84.8*
List 2				
K-IS-R	94.6*	64.5	43.8	59.9
KB-IS-R	93.9	90	89.3	91.5

Table 5. Precision, accuracy, sensitivity and F1 score values obtained for the models when testing them. Highlighted in bold are the highest values for each section. * Second highest values.

Regarding density estimations, to obtain usable models, the predictions were extended to a $\pm 5\%$ deviation (10% range) from the human assessment. In this continuous ground truth test (Table 6), the best performing model overall was the model K-IS, with an F score of 42.7%. Closely followed by the model KB-IS-R, which precision points drops, but F score closes up to K-IS with a 41.9%.

Ground truth for *Zostera marina* – Continuous 10% range

Model	Precision	Accuracy	Sensitivity	F1 score
List 1				
K-IS	53.9*	54.5	28	42.7
KB-IS	36	53	22.3	36.4
List 2				
K-IS-R	56.3	53.5*	25.6	40
KB-IS-R	38.2	53	28	41.9*

Table 6. Precision, accuracy, sensitivity and F1 score values obtained for the models when testing them. Highlighted in bold are the highest values for each section. * Second highest values.

Figure 3. Binary (presence-absence) representation of the predictions obtained with KB-IS-R model. A – Borno Oceanographic station area. B – Kristineberg Marine Laboratory area. (*Lantmateriet, 2024; LstO Ålgräs- och natingångar 2019-2024*)

Figure 4. Continuous (density estimations) representation of the predictions obtained with KB-IS-R model. A – Borno Oceanographic station area. B – Kristineberg Marine Laboratory area. (*Lantmateriet, 2024; LstO Ålgräs- och natingångar 2019-2024*)

Map creation

The model used to create the maps (Figure 3 and 4) was the KB-IS-R, as it presented the highest F-score (combined) regarding presence-absence (Table 5) and density estimations (Table 6). When compared to eelgrass records from 2018 to 2023 (LstO Ålgräs- och natingångar 2019-2024), the rasters obtained through the estimation and extrapolation of this model predictions, mostly coincided with official reports. Due to the few transects recorded and the extrapolation of the values, the resolution of the maps descended. Nevertheless, we can see a high percentage of matching. In both representations (Figure 3 and 4) some areas do not coincide, showing a possible loss of meadow surface

Discussion

Metrics tell us that the best performing models were the reduced models, which contained lesser classes. K-IS-R, which was trained with data from only one site, showed higher class recognition capabilities, while KB-IS-R showed higher precision. For presence-absence, the models that showed the best performance were KB-IS and KB-IS-R, being nearly perfect at predicting the presence of *Zostera marina*, with F-scores surpassing 0.8 (Table 5 and 6). Regarding the density estimation of *Zostera marina* meadows, the best model was K-IS. Although not foolproof, its main failure was to overestimate the coverage of eelgrass (Table 5 and 6). Overall, the chosen model was KB-IS-R.

The maps tell a different story (Figure 3 and 4), discrepancies between the official records and the predictions can be seen. They can be explained due to several reasons, firstly, the model was used in frames extracted at fixed intervals, with the objective of obtaining the most faithful image possible of the transect if these images overlapped. This provided a corridor of 35 centimetres for each transect with predictions obtained using the most reliable model. Then the data points were extrapolated to achieve larger results, being the output approximated values of what could be found on the field. The extrapolation tool provides new predictions based on the numbers found on each square that forms the line. Therefore, the maps are predictions of presence-absence and coverage established through similarity. Secondly, official records were taken from 2019 to 2023, a 4-year period. Due to high costs and time constraints, it can be safely assumed that each area was studied once, rather than revisited each year of the process. Therefore, the difference between predictions and records can be partially explained by changes in the environment (i.e. the eelgrass cover) during the last few years. Finally, this methodology only uses ROVs, if supported with aerial or satellite imagery, better shaped maps could be created.

Since these models were trained using underwater footage, the training can be viewed as being skewed due to the low quality and poor conditions that this environment provides. Therefore, there was a conscious effort to record during good and bad days, with good lighting (usage of flashlights) and adjusting the camera settings to underwater recording as a counter measure. These aspects of the methodology can explain part of the predicted errors found in the testing.

Usage of deep learning models for vegetation monitoring remains a relatively niche but developing field. In the few other projects that can be found, the models used are Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) (Nielsen et al., 2023), YOLO or CNN (Weinbach et al., 2025). In these articles similar conclusions were reached, deep learning models can be a good method to study *Zostera marina* (and other species if trained for it). It is important to note that various models can be used if tuned to the method, proving that different

resources can achieve the same result. However, the data is currently lacking as more research is needed.

Compared to other projects, we can also highlight promising results due to the few annotations used in this project. Current studies work with thousands of annotations and frames. Our results were obtained using less than 700 annotations per model. Being proof of how new models are in fact becoming more optimal for training and research. In addition, it was shown that with limited resources and a small ROV, a 70.000m² mapping project can be done in one morning – if weather provides. Therefore, we could call the project a success regarding optimization compared to traditional methods.

The next step would be to study how these same models perform when applied to other species, such as *Fucus serratus*, or sea floor identification. This would offer a preview of how interdisciplinary models can perform. Another direction would be to test this location specific models in a different environment - similar to before, we would obtain models that function globally capable of accomplishing different objectives.

The limitations of this type of methodology are obvious, currently there is not enough data to firmly state that this form of monitoring is the most optimal or the most accurate when mapping eelgrass meadows. However, we cannot ignore the results, the evolution of these models proves that there is a high chance of reducing the human load within the investigation field.

Conclusion

Several high performing models, both for presence-absence studies and density estimations, were obtained, being viable for creating maps of the estimated presence and density for *Zostera marina*. Although low resolution, the maps showed potential for future use. They were also successfully used to study large areas in a short amount of time, with very few resources. The top performer nonetheless was KB-IS-R.

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